

DRUGS IN PAMA

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INTRODUCTION

Twak Dosha is one of the common diseases. There is no satisfactory treatment in any other system of medicine except in Ayurveda where a lot of description about its etiopathogenesis and treatment is available right from the Vedic and Samhita period.

In the present study focussed on Pama one of the skin disorders. 75 cases of this disease entity have been studied and reported in the present paper.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The cases under study were thoroughly investigated and examined on Ayurvedic parameters. However, routine investigation like urine, stool, blood for TLC, DLC, Hb% have been done in all the cases. Only uncomplicated cases of Pama have been included in the present study. In some of the cases VDRL, Blood Sugar, Kahn's test and Nasal smear for Bacillus

Lepra were done wherever necessary so as to exclude any other pathology.

The assessment of cases was done from Ayurvedic point of view keeping in view the clinical and symptomatological improvement. The study on Prakriti, Sara, Samhanan, Satva, Agni, Kostha, Bala was done in each and every case.

In the present study 75 cases of Pama were administered the following group of medicines

1. Gandhaka Kaipa 1 gm. Thrice a day with Triphala Choorna 1 gm. simple water.
2. Kaishore guggulu-3 tabs, B. D. with mitk.
3. Maha Marichyaadi taila - for massage.
4. Jatyadi tailat+Yashad Pushpa bhasm = Malahar for external application.

Few cases were taking some of the strong allopathic drugs at the time of their reporting and these drugs were gradually tapered off.

Patients were lavalled as

1. Alpa Prasham - (25% relief)
2. Ardhaprasham - (50% relief)
3. Prasham - (75% relief)
4. Poorna Prasham (100% relief)

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

The present study covers a total number of 75 cases of Pama out of which eighteen got 25% relief, forty two patients got 50% relief, eight patients got 75% relief and seven patients got 100% relief.

The result of treatment of there cases of Pama in relation to their age group and sex group is shown in Table 1 and 2. The duration of treatment has been shown in table 3.

Table 1: Age and Pama.

Age Group	No. of Cases	Age group in years (Percentage)
1 to 14	5	6.06
15 to 39	40	53.03
31 to 45	14	18.66
45 to 60	10	13.33
61 and above	6	8.00
Total	75	100

The maximum cases belong to the age group of 15 to 30 years.

Table 2: Sex group.

S.No.	Class of the Patient	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Male	62	82.67
2.	Female	13	17.33
	Total	75	100.00

In the present study the incidence of this disease was 5 times higher in the male than in female.

Table 3: Duration of treatment in weeks.

S.No.	Weeks	No. of the cases
1	Upto 2 weeks	04
2	2 to 4 weeks	30
3	4 to 6 weeks	05
4	6 to 8 weeks	15
	8 weeks and above	20
	Total	75

Symptoms

The following were the main symptoms found in majority of the cases in the present study

1. Kandoo, 2. pidaka, 3. Pak, 4. Srava, 5. Daha, 6. Vedana Prakriti, sara, samhanan, satva, bala, agni and kostha have been shown in table no. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8,9 and 10 respectively as shown below.

Table 4: Prakriti Study.

S.No.	Name of Prakriti	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Vata Paittika	35	46.66
2	Vata Shlaishmic	10	13.33
3	Shlaishma Paittika	30	40.00
		75	100.00

The persons who belong to Vata Paittik Prakriti were more prone to skin ailments than that of shleshma paittika prakriti.

Table 5: Sara Study.

S.No.	Name of Sara	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Twak Sara	22	29.34
2	Rakta Sara	1	1.33
3	Mamsa Sara	10	13.33
4	Meda Sara	1	1.33
5	Ashti Sara	15	20.00
6	Majja Sara	13	17.34
7	Sukra Sara	0	0
8	Twagasthi Sara	10	13.33
9	Twakmajja Sara	3	4.00
		75	100.00

Twak sara, Ashti sara and Majja sara persons who were noted to be suffering from the Twak doshas disorders.

Table 6: Samhanan Study.

S.No.	Name of Samhanan	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Alpha Samhat	30	40
2	Samhat	30	40
3	Susamhata	15	20
		75	100.00

Table 7: Satva Study.

S.No.	Name of Satva	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Pravar Satva	0	0
2	Madhyam Satva	67	89.34
3	Heena Satva	8	10.66
		75	100.00

The Madhyam Satva persons were found to be maximum.

Table 8: Bala Study.

S.No.	Name of Bala	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Uttam Bala	0	0
2	Madhyam Bala	62	82.67
3	Heena Bala	13	17.33
		75	100.00

Maximum number of the patients were from the Madhyam Bala group.

Table 9: Agni Study.

S.No.	Name of Agni	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Samagni	64	86.94
2	Visamagni	3	4.06
3	Teevragni	0	0
4	Mandagni	8	10.00
		75	100.00

The present study has proved that agni generally does not deteriorate much in the cases of Pama. Only 8, out of 75 cases has Mandagni whereas 67 cases had Samagni.

Table 9: Koshtha Study.

S.No.	Name of Koshtha	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Mridukoshtha	3	4.00
2	Madhya Koshtha	42	56.00
3	Kroor Koshtha	30	40.00
		75	100.00

Generally patients of either Madhyam Koshtha of the Kroor koshtha suffered from the skin disorder.

Summary and Conclusion

75 cases of Pama have been treated with the Ayurvedic medicine showed significant results as shown in table.

Table 10: Result in Percentage.

S.No.	Name of Result	No. of Cases	Percentage
1	Alp Prasham (25% relief)	18	24.00
2	Ardha Prasham (50% relief)	42	56.00
3	Prashama (75% relief)	08	10.66
4	Poorna Prasham (100% relief)	07	9.33
		75	100.00

The symptoms involved, Prakriti, Sara, Samhanan, Satva, Bala, Agni and Koshta pareeksha have been analysed and reported. No toxicity of the drug was observed in the doses administered in any of the case.